

A study on the Cymidae, Blissidae, Artheneidae, Heterogastridae, Oxycarenidae, Berytidae and Piesmatidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Lygaeoidea) fauna of Amasya Province, Türkiye

Dilan Eser¹ Ahmet Dursun^{2*}

¹Amasya University, Faculty of Arts and Science, Department of Biology, Türkiye. E-mail: dilann.m2106@gmail.com ORCID iD: 0000-0002-5957-4389

§: This study was produced from the MSc thesis.

²Amasya University, Faculty of Arts and Science, Department of Biology, Türkiye. E-mail: ahmet.dursun@amasya.edu.tr ORCID iD: 0000-0002-5114-7470

*Corresponding author, e-mail: ahmet.dursun@amasya.edu.tr

ABSTRACT: This work aimed to determine the families Cymidae, Blissidae, Artheneidae, Heterogastridae, Oxycarenidae, Berytidae, and Piesmatidae in Amasya province. In result of the identification of the material collected revealed 22 species belonging to 16 genera of 7 families. All species are new records for the Amasya province and 9 species were recorded for the first time from the Black Sea region and 7 species were also new records for the central Black Sea region. Additionally, *Gampsocoris culicinus* Seidenstücker, 1948 (Berytidae), known from Anatolia so far only from Malatya, was recorded for the second time for Anatolia in our present study area.

KEY WORDS: Heteroptera, Lygaeoidea, new records, Amasya, Türkiye .

To cite this article: Eser, D., Dursun, A., 2023, A study on the Cymidae, Blissidae, Artheneidae, Heterogastridae, Oxycarenidae, Berytidae and Piesmatidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Lygaeoidea) fauna of Amasya Province, Türkiye, *J.Het.Turk.*, 5(2): 285-298

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10207343

To link to this article: <https://www.j-ht.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/V52-A9.pdf>

Received: Nov 14, 2023; **Revised:** Nov 22, 2023; **Accepted:** Nov 24, 2023; **Published online:** Nov 30, 2023

INTRODUCTION

The Heteroptera Latreille, 1810 with terrestrial, aquatic, and semiaquatic species is the most diverse suborder of Hemiptera, including approximately 45.000 species belonging to 24 superfamilies belonging to seven infraorder in the world, and in the Palaearctic region 1632 genera, and nearly 9365 described species (Henry, 2017; Péricart, 2001). Among these species, 1650 species are distributed in Türkiye (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2015, 2017, 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2017, 2023). The superfamily Lygaeoidea Schilling, 1829 is known in the world with 4290 species belonging to 708 genera of 17 families (Henry, 2017). Among them, most 1000 species belonging to 242 genera of 14 families were mentioned from the Palaearctic region according to the available records so far (Péricart, 2001). All species are terrestrial of the superfamily Lygaeoidea and distributed in almost all habitats (Péricart, 2001).

The subfamilies Cyminae, Blissinae, Artheneinae, Heterogastrinae, and Oxycareninae were within the family Lygaeidae but these polyphyletic subfamilies were elevated to family status by Henry (2017). The families Cymidae Baerensprung, 1860, Blissidae Stål, 1862, Artheneidae Stål, 1872, Heterogastridae Stål, 1872, Oxycarenidae Stål, 1862, Berytidae Fieber, 1851, and Piesmatidae Amyot & Serville, 1843 are small taxa in terms of the number of species. The family Piesmatidae includes 2 genera and 19 species in the Palaearctic region. Of those, 6 species belonging to 2 genera are distributed in Türkiye. All species are phytophagous and feeding especially on Caryophyllaceae and Chenopodiaceae (Heiss & Péricart, 2001). The other rather little family Berytidae includes 54 species belonging to 13 genera in the Palaearctic region. 19 species of 5 genera were mentioned from Türkiye (Péricart, 2001; Kment & Fent, 2012). Of those, the type localities of *Gampsocoris culicinus melitenus* Seidenstücker, 1965,

Gampsocoris enslini Seidenstücker, 1953 and *Neides brevipennis* Puton, 1895 are in Türkiye (Dursun & Fent, 2017). The Family Cymidae includes 5 genera and 22 species from Palaearctic region. In Türkiye, 7 species belonging to the 2 genera are mentioned. *Cymus turcicus* Matocq, 2000 belonging to the family Cymidae is an endemic species from Türkiye (Péricart, 2001). 8 genera and 56 species belonging to the Blissidae family are distributed in the Palaearctic region. In Türkiye, 7 species belonging to 3 genera are known. The Family Artheneidae includes 4 genera and 16 species from Palaearctic region. 8 species belonging to 2 genera are distributed in Türkiye. The Oxycarenidae is a relatively richer family in terms of the number of species compared to the others. 63 species belonging to 19 genera are known in the Palaearctic region. Of these, 9 genera and 15 species have been recorded from Türkiye. The family Heterogastridae includes 11 genera and 24 species from Palaearctic region. 5 species belonging to 2 genera are distributed in Türkiye (Péricart, 2001).

The discovery of the Heteroptera fauna of Amasya, which is an important province in the Central Black Sea Region, is important for the biodiversity of Türkiye. Amasya has different biotopes and microclimate areas with its mountains, plains, and valleys. It needs further studies on the Biodiversity of Lygaeoidea from Amasya. Therefore, this study aims to bring forth the Biodiversity of the families of Lygaeoidea fauna of Amasya.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was carried out with adult 182 males and 150 females collected from 29 different localities in Amasya province in the years 2020 to 2021 (Figure 1). The specimens were collected from under herbaceous vegetation and above ground with a sweep net and aspirator. All specimens were put in tubes in 70% ethanol and brought to the

Figure 1. The area of Cymidae, Blissidae, Artheneidae, Heterogastridae, Oxycarenidae, Berytidae and Piesmatidae study in Amasya (from google earth).

laboratory. In the laboratory, as in our previous studies, the specimens were softened in hot water (90°C-100°C) for preparation of the male genitalia which was used for further identifications. The specimens were prepared and identified using the relevant diagnostic was investigated under a stereomicroscope (Leica EZ4) and keys of Stichel (1960), and Péricart, 1999a, b). The material is deposited in the collection of Amasya University, Faculty of Science and Arts, Department of Biology (Amasya, Türkiye).

RESULTS

Hemiptera Linnaeus, 1758

Heteroptera Latreille, 1810

Cymidae Baerensprung, 1860

Cyminae Baerensprung, 1860

Tribus: Cymini Baerensprung, 1860

Genus: *Cymus* Hahn, 1832

Cymus claviculus (Fallen, 1807)

Material examined: Amasya: Taşova: Kızılgüdüren, 10.07.2020, 1♂, 3♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Bartın, Bursa, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Hatay, İzmir, Karaman, Kahramanmaraş, Kocaeli, Konya, Mersin, Muğla, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1901; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Önder et al., 1981, 2006; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yazıcı et al., 2023).

Distribution in Palearctic Region:

Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan (European part), Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal,

Romania, Russia (South European Part), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine **North Africa:** Algeria, Canary Islands, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Cyprus, Georgia, Israel, Jordan Kazakhstan (Asian part), Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Russia (Eastern and Western Siberian Regions), Syria, Tajikistan, Türkiye (Asian part), Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2020).

***Cymus glandicolor* Hahn, 1832**

Material examined: Amasya: Taşova: 27.05.2021, Arpaderesi, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Antalya, Bartın, Bursa, Hatay, İstanbul, Karaman, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kastamonu, Kocaeli, Kütahya, Kırşehir, Osmaniye, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1901, 1918; Kiritshenko, 1918; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Dursun, 2016; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:

Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kosovo, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Northern, Southern and Central European Region), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine.: Azerbaijan, China (North, Northeast, Southwest, Western Plateau), Georgia, Japan, Kazakhstan (Asian part), Korea, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Russia (Far East, Eastern and Western Siberia Regions), Tajikistan, Türkiye (Asian part), Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2020).

***Cymus melanocephalus* Fieber, 1861**

Material examined: Amasya: Suluova: Eraslan, 29.06.2021, 1♂; **Taşova:** Kızgüldüren, 10.07.2020, 14♂♂, 15♀♀; 27.05.2021, Arpaderesi, 24♂♂, 27♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Bartın, Bayburt, Bolu, Bursa,

Çanakkale, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Karabük, Karaman, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kocaeli, Konya, Konya, Kırşehir, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Sinop, Sivas, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1901, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al. 1999; Önder et al. 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al. 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016; Yence, 2019; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:

Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kosovo, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Southern European Region), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Kyrgyzstan, Syria, Tajikistan, Türkiye (Asian part), Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2020).

Blissidae Stål, 1862

Blissinae Stål, 1862

Genus: *Dimorphopterus* Stål, 1872

***Dimorphopterus blissoides* (Barensprung, 1859)**

Material examined: Amasya: Merzifon: Çavundur, 06.09.2020, 2♂♂, 2♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Mersin (Tarsus) (Péricart, 1999a); Elazığ (Çerçi et al., 2018).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:

Europe: Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Moldavia, Romania, Russia (South European Region), Serbia, Slovenia, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iraq, Israel, Türkiye (Asian part) (Aukema, 2020).

***Dimorphopterus doriae* (Ferrari, 1874)**

Material examined: Amasya: Center:

Dadıköy, 21.04.2021, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Aksaray, Bolu, Izmir, Niğde, Tokat, Yalova (Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:
Europe: Albania, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan (European part), Kosovo, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Romania, Russia (South European Region), Serbia, Slovakia, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Kazakhstan (Asian part), Syria, Türkiye (Asian part) (Aukema, 2020).

Genus: Ischnodemus Fieber, 1837

***Ischnodemus caspius* Jakovlev, 1871**

Material examined: Amasya: Göynücek: Gediksaray, 31.08.2020, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: İzmir (Péricart, 1999a), Kahramanmaraş (Lodos et al., 1999).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:
Europe: Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Russia (Southern Europe region), Serbia, Ukraine. **North Africa:** Egypt. **Asia:** Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Kazakhstan (Asian part), Kuwait, Syria, Tajikistan, Türkiye (Asian part), Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2020).

Artheneidae Stål, 1872

Artheneinae Stål, 1872

Tribus: Artheneini Stål, 1872

Genus: *Holcocranum* Fieber, 1860

***Holcocranum saturejae* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Material examined: Amasya: Center: Kızgüldüren, 10.07.2020, 22♂♂, 17♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Bursa, Edirne, Elazığ, Hatay, İzmir, Karaman, Kahramanmaraş, Kocaeli, Mersin (Önder et al., 1981, 1984; Çağatay, 1988; Péricart, 1999a; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:
Europe: Albania, Austria, Bulgaria,

Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan (European part), Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Netherlands, Romania, Russia (Southern European Region), Slovakia, Spain, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Azerbaijan, Israel, Jordan, Kyrgyzstan, Türkiye (Asian part), Turkmenistan. **Outside the Palaearctic:** North America, Tropical Africa (Chad, Ghana, Sudan and Tanzania) (Aukema, 2020).

Heterogastridae Stål, 1872

Heterogastrinae Stål, 1872

Genus: *Heterogaster* Schilling, 1829

***Heterogaster artemisiae* Schilling, 1829**

Material examined: Amasya: Center: Tatar, 19.05.2021, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Antalya, Düzce, Edirne, Erzurum, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Mersin, Niğde, Osmaniye (Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016; Yence, 2019).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:
Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia-Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kosovo, Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Central and southern European region), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Armenia, Azerbaijan, China (Northwest region), Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan (Asian part), Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Türkiye (Asian part), Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, (Aukema, 2020).

***Heterogaster urticae* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined: Amasya: Center: Sarıyar, 19.05.2021, 1♂, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Aksaray, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın,

Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çankırı, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Karaman, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Samsun, Trabzon, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1905a; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Çağatay, 1989; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2023; Yazıcı, 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region: **Europe:** Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Malta, Moldova, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Azores, Canary Islands, Egypt, Madeira, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Israel, Japan, Jordan, Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Russia (Western Siberia), Syria, Türkiye, Turkmenistan (Aukema, 2020).

Genus: *Platyplax* Fieber, 1860

Platyplax inermis (Rambur, 1839)

Material examined: Amasya: Center: Boğazköy, 18.05.2020, 4♂♂, 4♀♀; **Gümüşhacıköy:** Gümüş, 07.09.2021, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çanakkale, İzmir, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Mersin (Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region: **Europe:** Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Montenegro, Portugal, Spain. **North Africa:** Algeria, Canary Islands, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Cyprus, Israel, Türkiye (Asian part), Yemen. **Outside the Palaearctic Region:** Ethiopia (Aukema, 2020).

Oxycarenidae Stål, 1862

Oxycareninae Stål, 1862

Genus: *Brachyplax* Fieber, 1860

Brachyplax tenuis (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)

Material examined: Amasya: Center: Kaleköy, 28.04.2021, 1♂; **Taşova:** Gürsu, 27.05.2021, 1♂, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Edirne, Elazığ, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Mersin, Niğde (Horváth, 1901; Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999b, 2001; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:

Europe: Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Southern European Region), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia.

Asia: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Cyprus, Georgia, Israel, Kazakhstan (Asian part), Kyrgyzstan, Syria, Tajikistan, Türkiye (Asian part), Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2020).

Genus: *Macroplax* Fieber, 1860

Macroplax fasciata (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)

Material examined: Amasya: Center: Yassıçal, 28.04.2021, 1♂, 3♀♀; **Sarıyar,** 19.05.2021, 1♂, 1♀; **Taşova:** Çaydibi, 27.05.2021, 1♂; **Gümüşhacıköy:** Gümüş, 07.09.2021, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Karaman, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırşehir, Konya, Kocaeli, Kütahya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Osmaniye, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Uşak, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1905b; Fahringer, 1922; Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956;

Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Çağatay, 1985; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region: **Europe:** Albania, Andorra, Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Germany, Great Britain (Jersey), Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Malta, Moldova, Montenegro, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Southern European Region), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Canary Islands, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Cyprus, Georgia, Israel, Lebanon, Syria, Türkiye (Asian part) (Aukema, 2020).

Genus: *Microplax* Fieber, 1860

***Microplax albofasciata* (A. Costa, 1847)**

Material examined: Amasya: Taşova: Çaydibi, 27.05.2021, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bursa, Edirne, Gaziantep, İstanbul, Karaman, Kayseri, Kütahya, Mersin, Tekirdağ, Uşak (Horváth, 1883; Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Péricart, 1999b; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region: **Europe:** Albania, Andorra, Belgium?, Bosnia Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Holland, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Montenegro, Slovenia, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Spain, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine, **Asia:** Syria, Israel, Türkiye (Asian part). **North Africa:** Algeria, Tunisia (Aukema, 2020).

***Microplax interrupta* (Fieber, 1837)**

Material examined: Amasya: Center: Yassıçal, 28.04.2021, 1♀; İpekköy, 16.05.2021, 2♂♂, 7♀♀; Ezinepazar, 19.05.2021, 4♂♂, 5♀♀; **Suluova:** Eraslan, 28.06.2021, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kayseri, Konya, Kırşehir, Mardin, Mersin (Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016; Bolu, 2020; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region: **Europe:** Albania, Andorra, Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan (European part), Kosovo, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Southern European Part), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia!, Spain, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Canary Islands, Egypt, Madeira, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Armenia, Azerbaijan?, China (Northwest Region), Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Kazakhstan (Asian part), Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Mongolia, Syria, Tajikistan, Türkiye (Asian part), Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. **Outside the Palaearctic:** India (Péricart, 2001).

Genus: *Oxycarenus* Fieber, 1837

Subgenus: *Euoxycarenus* Samy, 1969

***Oxycarenus pallens* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850)**

Material examined: Amasya: Center: Sarıyar, 19.05.2021, 3♂♂, 1♀; Uygur, 19.05.2021, 1♂; Ezinepazar, 19.05.2021, 2♂♂, 1♀; Tatar, 19.05.2021, 1♀; İpekköy, 16.05.2021, 2♂♂, 1♀; Boğazköy, 28.06.2021, 6♂♂, 1♀; **Suluova:** Yüzbeyi, 28.06.2021, 2♂♂; Eraslan, 28.06.2021, 1♀; Ayrancı, 28.06.2021, 1♀; **Taşova:** Kızgüldüren, 10.07.2020, 1♂; Alpaslan, 27.05.2021, 2♀♀; Arpaderesi, 27.05.2021, 1♂, 1♀; Yeşilyurt, 27.05.2021, 1♂, 1♀; Gürsu, 1♂, 1♀; **Göynücek:** İkizyaka, 03.09.2021, 2♂♂, 1♀; **Gümüşhacıköy:** Gümüş, 29.08.2020, 1♀; 07.09.2021, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bolu, Burdur, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum,

Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Karabük, Karaman, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kilis, Konya, Kırıkkale, Kırşehir, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Van, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Çağatay, 1985; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Matocq & Özgen, 2010; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2023; Fent & Dursun, 2016; Bolu, 2020; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:

Europe: Albania, Austria, Bosnia-Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan (European part), Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro Portugal, Romania, Russia (Central and Southern European Part), Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Canary Islands, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Afghanistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, China, Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kazakhstan (Asian part), Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Mongolia, Syria, Tajikistan, Türkiye (Asian part), Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Yemen. **Outside the Palaearctic:** India, Sudan (Aukema, 2020).

Subgenus: Oxycareus Fieber, 1837

Oxycareus hyalinipennis (A. Costa, 1843)

Material examined: Amasya: Center: İpekköy, 16.05.2021, 1♀; Şeyhçui, 22.08.2021, 3♂♂, 6♀♀; Hakimiyet Park, 58♂♂, 24♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kilis, Konya, Mersin, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sinop (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Çağatay, 1985; Péricart, 1999b; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Şerban, 2010; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2023; Yazıcı, 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:

Europe: Austria, Bosnia-Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain. **North Africa:** Algeria, Canary Islands, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Afghanistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan?, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Saudi Arabia, Sinai Peninsula (Egypt), Syria, Türkiye (Asian part), Yemen. **Outside the Palaearctic:** Eastern Region, South America, Tropical and Southern Africa (Aukema, 2020).

Berytidae Fieber, 1851

Berytinae Fieber, 1851

Tribus: Berytini Fieber, 1851

Genus: Apoplymus Fieber, 1859

Apoplymus pectoralis Fieber, 1859

Material examined: Amasya: Taşova: 27.05.2021, Sepetli, 1♂; 07.09.2021, Gümüş, 1♂, 2♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Balıkesir, İzmir (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2016).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:

Europe: Albania, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Spain, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Lebanon, Syria, Türkiye (Asian part) (Aukema, 2020).

Genus: Neides Latreille, 1802

Neides tipularius (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: Amasya: Gümüşhacıköy: 07.09.2021, Maden, 3♂♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Bingöl, Çankırı, Edirne, Elazığ, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri (Önder et al., 2006; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015, Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:

Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia-Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland,

Italy, Kosovo, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (South, Northern and Central European Region), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Türkiye (European part), Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Kazakhstan (Asian part), Russia (Western, Siberian Region), Türkiye (Asian part), Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2020).

Tribus: Berytinini Southwood & Leston, 1959

Genus: Berytinus Kirkaldy, 1900

Subgenus: Lizinus Mulsant & Rey, 1870

Berytinus geniculatus (Horváth, 1885)

Material examined: Amasya: Merzifon: 06.09.2020, Çavundur, 1♂, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: İzmir, Kahramanmaraş (Önder et al., 2006; Kiyak, 2016).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Moldova, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Southern European region), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Canary Islands, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iraq, Israel?, Türkiye (Asian part) (Aukema, 2020).

Gampsocorinae Southwood & Leston, 1959

Tribus: Gampsocorini Southwood & Leston, 1959

Genus: Gampsocoris Fuss, 1852

Gampsocoris culicinus Seidenstücker, 1948

Material examined: Amasya: Göynücek: 03.09.2021, İkizyaka, 1♂; **Gümüşhacıköy:** 07.09.2021, Gümüş, 2♂♂, 6♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Edirne, Malatya (Seidenstücker, 1965; Kothe et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kosovo, Macedonia, Moldova, Romania, Russia (Southern European Region), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Morocco. **Asia:** Kazakhstan (Asian part), Kyrgyzstan, Russia (Western, East Siberian Region), Türkiye (Asian part) (Aukema, 2020).

Metacanthinae Douglas & Scott, 1865

Tribus: Metacanthini Douglas & Scott, 1865

Genus: Metacanthus A. Costa, 1843

Subgenus: Metacanthus A. Costa, 1843

Metacanthus meridionalis (A. Costa, 1843)

Material examined: Amasya: 28.06.2021, Boğazköy, 4♂♂, 4♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Balıkesir, Bursa, Bitlis, Hakkari, İzmir, Manisa, Mardin (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2016).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region: Europe: Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kosovo, Macedonia, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Southern European Region), Serbia, Spain, Ukraine. **Asia:** Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Türkiye (Asian part), Yemen. (Aukema, 2020).

Piesmatidae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Piesmatinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus: Piesma Lepeletier & Serville, 1828

Piesma maculatum (Laporte, 1833)

Material examined: Amasya: Center: Dadı, 21.04.2021, 2♂♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Balıkesir, Çankırı, Erzurum (Yıldırım & Özbek, 1990; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Önder et al.,

2006; Yazıcı et al., 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic Region:

Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan (European part), Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Malta, Moldavia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (South, Northern and Central European Region), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Armenia, Azerbaijan, China (North and Northeast Region), Georgia, Japan, Kazakhstan (Asian part), Korea, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Russia (West, East and Far East Siberia Region), Türkiye (Asian part), Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2020).

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

We examined in this study a total of 332 (182 males and 150 females) adult specimens.

As a result of the determination of the material collected in Amasya province, 3 species belonging to 1 genera of Cymidae, 3 species belonging to 2 genera of Blissidae, 1 species belonging to 1 genera of Artheneidae, 3 species belonging to 2 genera of Heterogastridae, 6 species belonging to 4 genera of Oxycarenidae, 5 species belonging to 5 genera of Berytidae and 1 species belonging to 1 genera of Piesmatidae families were recorded. All species are new records for the Amasya province.

In addition, among these species, *Dimorphopterus blissoides*, *Ischnodemus caspius*, *Holcocranum saturejae*, *Microplax albofasciata*, *Apoplymus pectoralis*, *Berytinus geniculatus*, *Gampsocoris culicinus*, *Metacanthus meridionalis* and *Piesma maculatum* were recorded for the first time from the Black Sea Region and *Cymus clavicularis*, *Cymus glandicolor*, *Heterogaster artemisiae*, *Platyplax*

inermis, *Brachyplax tenuis*, *Microplax interrupta* and *Neides tipularius* were also new records for the Central Black Sea Region (Table 1).

Dimorphopterus blissoides a rarely distributed species, was until now only known from Mersin (Péricart, 1999a) in the Mediterranean Region and from Elazığ in east Anatolia (Çerçi et al., 2018) and *Ischnodemus caspius* from İzmir (Péricart, 1999a) in western Anatolia and from Kahramanmaraş in Mediterranean Region (Lodos et al., 1999), and *Apoplymus pectoralis*, from Balıkesir and İzmir in western Anatolia (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2016).

Berytinus geniculatus was recorded from Kahramanmaraş in the Mediterranean Region and İzmir in western Anatolia, *Gampsocoris culicinus* was recorded from Edirne in the Thrace Region and Malatya in the eastern Anatolia Region (Seidenstücker, 1965; Kothe et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Kiyak, 2016).

In this study, these species were recorded for the third time. The northernmost limit of the distribution of these species in Türkiye was also given in this study.

It was known that among the identified species, *Platyplax inermis*, *Neides tipularius*, and *Metacanthus meridionalis* are rare species in Türkiye. In addition, it was determined that the population densities of all species except *Oxycarenus hyalipennis*, *Oxycarenus pallens*, *Cymus melanocephalus*, and *Holcocranum saturae* were quite low in the research area.

Yıldırım & Özbek (1990) stated that *Piesma maculatum* causes damage to sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Chenopodiaceae)) in Türkiye.

There are many farmers engaged in sugar beet production in Amasya, and if the population density of *Piesma maculatum* increases, it would have the potential to cause serious damage to Amasya sugar beet fields. However, we were able to detect only two examples of this species in our study.

Table 1. List of Cymidae, Blissidae, Artheneidae, Heterogastridae, Oxycarenidae Berytidae and Piesmatidae species of Amasya province. (A: Amasya, C: Central Black Sea Region, B: Black Sea Region, N: Number of Localities detected, S: Specimens)

Nu	Family	Species	A	C	B	N	S
1		<i>Cymus clavicolus</i> (Fallen, 1807)		+		1 locality	1♂, 3♀♀
2	Cymidae Baerensprung, 1860	<i>Cymus glandicolor</i> Hahn, 1832		+		1 locality	1♂
3		<i>Cymus melanocephalus</i> Fieber, 1861		+		3 localities	39♂♂, 42♀♀
4		<i>Dimorphopterus blissoides</i> (Baerensprung, 1859)			+	1 locality	2♂♂, 2♀♀
5	Blissidae Stål, 1862	<i>Dimorphopterus doriae</i> (Ferrari, 1874)		+		1 locality	1♀
6		<i>Ischnodemus caspius</i> Jakovlev, 1871			+	1 locality	1♀
7	Artheneidae Stål, 1872	<i>Holcocranum saturejiae</i> (Kolenati, 1845)			+	1 locality	22♂♂, 17♀♀
8		<i>Heterogaster artemisiae</i> Schilling, 1829		+		1 locality	1♀
9	Heterogastridae Stål, 1872	<i>Heterogaster urticae</i> (Fabricius, 1775)		+		1 locality	1♂, 1♀
10		<i>Platyplax inermis</i> (Rambur, 1839)		+		2 localities	5♂♂, 4♀♀
11		<i>Brachyplax tenuis</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)		+		2 localities	2♂♂, 1♀
12		<i>Macropfax fasciata</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)		+		4 localities	4♂♂, 4♀♀
13	Oxycarenidae Stål, 1862	<i>Microplax albofasciata</i> (A. Costa, 1847)			+	1 locality	1♀
14		<i>Microplax interrupta</i> (Fieber, 1837)		+		4 localities	7♂♂, 13♀♀
15		<i>Oxycarenus pallens</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850)		+		16 localities	22♂♂, 15♀♀
16		<i>Oxycarenus hyalinipennis</i> (A. Costa, 1843)		+		3 localities	61♂♂, 31♀♀
17		<i>Apolymsus pectoralis</i> Fieber, 1859			+	2 localities	2♂♂, 2♀♀
18		<i>Neides tipularius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		+		1 locality	3♂♂
19	Berytidae Fieber, 1851	<i>Berytinus geniculatus</i> (Horváth, 1885)			+	1 locality	1♂, 1♀
20		<i>Gampsocoris culicinus</i> Seidenstücker, 1948			+	2 localities	3♂♂, 6♀♀
21		<i>Metacanthus meridionalis</i> (A. Costa, 1843)			+	1 locality	4♂♂, 4♀♀
22	Piesmatidae Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Piesma maculatum</i> (Laporte, 1833)			+	1 locality	2♂♂

Regional studies are very important in revealing the fauna of a country. In this regard, the findings obtained in this study are important. The additional records obtained in this study also contribute to the biodiversity of the Cymidae, Blissidae, Artheneidae, Heterogastridae, Oxycarenidae, Berytidae, and Piesmatidae families in Amasya Province and its surroundings and the distribution data of the families in Türkiye.

REFERENCES

- Abacıgil, T. O., Varlı, S. V. & Tezcan, S., 2010, Heteroptera species determined by using hibernating trap bands in olive orchards near Edremit (Balıkesir) Bay, Türkiye. *Turkish Journal of Entomology*, 34(1): 105-115.
- Aukema, B. 2020. Catalogue of Palaearctic Heteroptera. Naturalis Biodiversity Center. Available from <https://catpalhet.linnaeus.naturalis.nl/> (Date accessed: 21.11.2023).
- Bolu, H., 2020, Southeastern Anatolia Region

- Insect Fauna II (Order Hemiptera I: Suborder Heteroptera II: Tingioidea, Reduvidae, Aradoidea, Coreoidea, Lygaeoidea) of Türkiye. *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 15 (1): 121-139.
- Çağatay, N., 1985, Türkiye Oxycareninae (Heteroptera-Lygaeidae) alt familyasının taksonomisi ve erkek genital organının önemi üzerine çalışmalar, *Bitki Koruma Bülteni*, 25: 18-29.
- Çağatay, N., 1988, Some Artheneinae from Turkey (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae), *Türkiye Entomoloji Dergisi*, 12: 201-208.
- Çağatay, N., 1989, Systematical studies on the Heterogasterine of Turkey (Heteroptera: Lygaeidae), *Turkish Journal of Entomology*, 13: 5-14.
- Çerçi, B. & Koçak, Ö. 2017, Further contribution to the Heteroptera (Hemiptera) fauna of Turkey with a new synonymy. *Acta Biologica Turcica*, 30: 121-127.
- Çerçi, B. & Özgen, İ. & Dioli, 2018, Additional faunistic notes on Heteroptera (Hemiptera: Insecta) in East Anatolia (Turkey). *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 6(1): 1225-1231.
- Çerçi, B. & Özgen, İ., 2021, Contribution to the Knowledge of Heteroptera (Hemiptera) Fauna of Elazığ Province with a New Record for the Fauna of Turkey, *Journal of the Heteroptera of Turkey*, 3(1): 50-75.
- Çerçi, B. & Koçak, Ö., 2023, Heteroptera (Hemiptera) fauna of Karaman with new records for Türkiye *Journal of the Heteroptera of Turkey*, 5(1): 10-128.
- Dursun, A. & Fent, M. 2015, Notes on some little known species of Heteroptera from Turkey with new records for the fauna of Europe and the Turkish Thrace. *North-Western Journal of Zoology*, 11(1): 92-96.
- Dursun, G., 2016, *Balıkesir kent ormanı ve BAUN Çağış yerleşkesindeki Heteroptera (Hemiptera) faunasının kışlak tuzaklarla belirlenmesi üzerinde araştırmalar*. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Balıkesir Üniversitesi, Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Balıkesir. Sayfa sayısı??
- Dursun, A. & Fent, M., 2017, Type Localities of Heteroptera (Insecta: Hemiptera) from Turkey. *Zootaxa*, 4227(4): 451-494.
- Dursun, A. & Fent, M., 2022, Türkiye'de dağılım gösteren istilacı Heteroptera (Insecta: Hemiptera) türlerinin ekonomik önemi. *İstilacı Zararlı Türler ve Mücadelesinde Yeni Yaklaşımlar*, 1: 145-171.
- Fent, M. & Japoshvili, G., 2012, Heteroptera (Insecta-Hemiptera) Fauna of Isparta-Gölcük Natural Park with some rare and peculiar species and new records for Mediterranean Region of Turkey. *Türkiye Entomoloji Bülteni*, 2(3): 149-164.
- Fent, M. & Dursun, A., 2016, Beiträge zur Lygaeidae-Fauna (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) des Westlichen Schwarzmeer-Gebietes in der Türkei. *Heteropteron*, 47: 30-36.
- Gadeau de Kerville, H., 1939, *Liste méthodique des invertébrés et des vertébrés récoltés en Asie-Mineure. Pp. 67-148 [Hemiptera pp. 116-125]*. In: *Voyage zoologique d'Henri Gadeau de Kerville en Asie-Mineure (avril-mai 1912). Tome 1, 1ère partie*. Paul Lechevalier, Paris.
- Google. <https://earth.google.com>
- Heiss, E. & Péricart, J., 2001, Family Piesmatidae Amyot & Serville, 1843, 221-226 pp. In: *Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region* (Eds. B. Aukema & Ch. Rieger) Pentatomomorpha I, Vol. 4. The Netherlands Entomological Society, Amsterdam, xiv+346pp.
- Henry, T. J., 2017, *Biodiversity of Heteroptera*, 279-335 pp. In: *Insect Biodiversity* (Eds. R. G. Foottit & P.H. Adler), Science and Society, Vol. I, Second edition. Wiley-Blackwell, Oxford.
- Hoberlandt, L., 1956, Results of the Zoological Scientific Expedition the National Museum in Praha to Turkey-18: Hemiptera IV: Terrestriale Hemiptera-Heteroptera of Turkey *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 3: 274.
- Horváth, G., 1883. Heteroptera Anatolica in regione Brussae collecta enumeravit. *Természetráji Füzetek*, 7: 21-30.
- Horváth, G., 1901, Hémiptères du voyage de M. Martinez Escalera dans l'Asie-Mineure. *Természetráji Füzetek*, 24: 469-485.
- Horváth, G., 1905a, Hemipteren. Ergebnisse einer naturwissenschaftlichen Reise zum Erdschias-Dagh (Kleinasien). Ausgeführt von Dr. Arnold Penther und Dr. Emerich Zederbauer. *Annalen. K.K. Naturhistorischen Hofmuseums*, 20: 179-189.
- Horváth, G., 1905b, Tingitidae novae vel minus cognitae e regione palaeartica,

- Annales Historico-Naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 3: 556-572.
- Horváth, G., 1918, Ad cognitionem faunae Hemipterorum Balcanicae, *Annales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 16: 321-340.
- Kiyak, S., 2016, On Heteroptera fauna of Binboğa Mountains (Turkey, Kahramanmaraş-Kayseri), *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 11: 441-449.
- Kiritshenko, A.N., 1918, Hemiptera-Heteroptera faunae Caucasiae. 1. Mémoires du Muséedu Caucase (A), 6, 1-177.
- Kment, P. & Fent, M., 2012. First record of *Metatropis rufescens* (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Berytidae) from Turkey, *Turkish Journal of Zoology*, 36(6): 828-830.
- Kothe, T., Blazi, G. & Schönitzer, K. 2004, Katalog der Wanzen-Typen von Gustav Seidenstücker (1912-1989) in der Zoologischen Staatssammlung München (Heteroptera). 61. *Bericht der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft*, Augsburg, 2004, 1-90.
- Küçükbasmacı, İ. & Kiyak, S., 2015, A Study on the Fauna of Heteroptera of Ilgaz Mountains (Kastamonu, Çankırı) With a New Record for Turkey, *Neuşehir Bilim ve Teknoloji Dergisi*, 4: 1-33.
- Linnavuori, R. E., 1953, A Palaearctic Heteropterous material collected by J. Sahlberg and U. Saalas, *Annales Entomologici Fennici*, 19: 147-167.
- Lodos, N., Önder, F., Pehlivan, E. & Atalay, R., 1978, *Ege ve Marmara bölgesinin zararlı böcek faunasının tesbiti üzerinde çalışmalar*. Curculionidae, Scarabaeidae (Coleoptera); Pentatomidae, Lygaeidae, Miridae (Heteroptera). Ziraî Mücadele ve Ziraî Karantina Genel Müdürlüğü, 135-169.
- Lodos, N., Önder, F., Pehlivan, E., Atalay, R., Erkin, E., Karsavuran, Y., Tezcan, S. & Aksoy, S., 1999, *Faunistic studies on Lygaeidae (Heteroptera) of Western Black Sea, Central Anatolia and Mediterranean Regions of Turkey*, E. Ü. Basımevi, İzmir, IX:1-58.
- Matocq, A. & Özgen, İ., 2010. A preliminary list of Heteroptera collected in Mardin and Siirt provinces from South-Eastern Anatolia of Turkey (Hemiptera), *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 5: 1011-1019.
- Matocq, A., Pluot-Sigwalt, D. & Özgen, İ., 2014, Terrestrial Hemiptera (Heteroptera) collected in South-East Anatolia (Diyarbakır, Mardin and Elazığ provinces) (Turkey): second list, *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 9(2): 884-930.
- Önder, F. & Adıgüzel, N., 1979, Some Heteroptera Collected by Light Trap in Diyarbakır (Turkey). *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi*, 3(1): 25-34.
- Önder, F., Ünal, A., Ünal, E., 1981. Kuzeybatı Anadolu kesiminde ışık tuzaklarında saptanan Heteroptera türleri. *Turkish Journal of Entomology*, 5(3), 151-169.
- Önder, F., Ünal, E. & Ünal, A., 1984, Heteropterous insects collected by light traps in Edirne (Turkey). *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi*, 8(4), 215-224.
- Önder, F., Karsavuran, Y., Tezcan, S. & Fent, M., 2006, *Heteroptera (Insecta) Catalogue of Türkiye*. İzmir, Türkiye, pp. 164.
- Péricart, J., 1999a, *Hémiptères Lygaeidae euro-méditerranéens*, volume 1. Faune de France. Vol. 84. Fédération Française des Sociétés de Sciences Naturelles, Paris, 475 pp.
- Péricart, J., 1999b. *Hémiptères Lygaeidae euro-méditerranéens*, volume 2. Faune de France. Vol. 84. Fédération Française des Sociétés de Sciences Naturelles, Paris, 453 pp.
- Péricart, J., 2001, Lygaeidae Schilling, 1829 – Seed-bugs (pp. 35-220). In: Aukema, B. & Rieger, C. (Eds). *Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region* 4. Netherlands Entomological Society, Amsterdam, Wageningen, Netherlands.
- Puton, A. & Noulhier, M., 1895, Supplement a la liste des Hemipteres d Akbes. *Revue d'Entomologie*, 14: 170-177.
- Seidenstücker, G., 1965, Beitrag zu *Gampsocoris* (Heteroptera, Berytidae), *Reichenbachia*, 5: 273-282.
- Stichel, W., 1960, *Illustrierte Bestimmungstabellen der Wanzen*. II. Europa, Berlin, 4(2-4): 34-118.
- Şerban, C., 2010, Faunistic Data on Some True Bugs Species (Insecta: Heteroptera) from West Turkey. *Travaux du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle*. 2010; LIII:171 - 180.
- Yazıcı, G., Yıldırım, E. & Moulet, P., 2015, Contribution to the knowledge of the Lygaeoidea (Hemiptera, Heteroptera) fauna of Turkey. *Linzer Biologische Beitrage*, 47

(1): 969–990.

Yazıcı, G., 2022, List of Pentatomomorpha (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) Described by Foreign Scientists in Nazife Tuatay Plant Protection Museum from Tukey. Part I, *Transactions of the American Entomological Society*, 148(2): 181-199.

Yazıcı, G., Bal, N. & Kıyak, S., 2023, Additional List of the Anthocoridae, Berytidae, Coreidae, Cydnidae, Lygaeidae, Nabidae,

Piesmatidae, Reduviidae, Rhopalidae, Scutelleridae, Tingidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) of Çankırı Province in Türkiye, *Journal of the Heteroptera of Turkey*, 5(1): 154-174.

Yence, K., 2019, *Aladağlar Milli Parkı Lygaeidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) faunası üzerine taksonomik ve faunistik çalışmalar* (Master's thesis, Trakya Üniversitesi, Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü-Edirne).